

GOAT ECTOPARASITOSIS

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Annotation: The article presents information on the spread of ectoparasites and ectoparasitises among goats.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada echkilar orasida uchrayotgan ektoparazit va ektoparazitozlarning tarqalishi bo'yicha ma'lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Keywords: Bovicolosis, lice, fleas, ticks, fleas, linognathosis, ctenocephalidosis, ripicephalioz, ectoparasite, ectoparasitosis.

Kalit so'zlar: Bovikolyoz, bit, burga, kana, junxo'r, linognatoz, ktenotsefalidoz, ripitsefalyoz, ektoparazit, ektoparazitoz.

Relevance of the topic. Goats are another type of livestock due to the fact that they do not require a lot of expenses for breeding, rapid reproduction and high fertility, the nutritional value of meat and dairy products, the necessity of wool, tweed and leather products for industry, their value, and the high demand for them. differs from animals. Goat breeding is a convenient and profitable sector for private and subsidiary farms. Because every family living in the village can increase their income by keeping and raising goats, consuming their milk and meat, making various products from goat's wool and wool, and selling it to the market. Various clothes and articles are made from the wool and wool of goats. Goat milk and meat are widely used as food. Goat's milk has healing and nutritional properties, especially milk from pasture-raised goats is the strongest salve for tuberculosis. Because pasture goats rarely get sick with tuberculosis.

The purpose of the study. It consists in studying the dynamics of fauna and seasonal distribution of ectoparasites and ectoparasitoses parasitizing goats in private and farms.

Research materials and methods. Modern recommendations and methodological manuals of parasitological, entomological, epizootological, microscopic examination, ecological-faunistic and veterinary parasitology sciences were used in the research.

Research results. 2023 research studies on the spread of ectoparasites causing ectoparasitic disease in goats, 90 goats at the Chavandoz farm, Nurabad district, Samarkand region, "Khudaykulov F.I." 60 goats on the livestock farm, 30 goats on the "Jamshid" farm, 31 goats belonging to U. Boboev, a resident of the "Boshkuduq" village, 327 goats belonging to "Nurobad Karakol Breeding" LLC, Nurota, Navoi region More than 645 heads belonging to Nurota Karakol Breeding Limited Liability Company, Orenburg white Angora goats, 375 belonging to Dami-ata farm, Nukus District, Republic of Karakalpakstan, total 1552 goats ectoparasites found from them were collected after parasitological examination and their morphology was studied,

species, sex, and systematics were determined. As a result, *B. caprae*, *Ctenocephalides caprae*, *Linognathidae caprae* and *Rh.* types of bursa ectoparasites and ectoparasites were determined (Table 1, Figures 1-2).

Ectoparasites and ectoparasitoses identified in goats

Table 1

T.r	Animal species	Ectoparasite species found	The name of ectoparasites	
1	In goats:	<i>Bovicola caprae</i>	Bovicolosis	entomosis
2		<i>Ctenocephalides caprae</i>	Ctenocephalidosis	entomosis
3		<i>Linognathidae caprae</i>	Linognathosis	entomosis
4		<i>Ripicephalus bursa</i>	Ripicephaliosis	arachnosis

Picture – 1. Parasitological examination process

Pictures 2. Found bovicolas.

Among goats, mainly *Bovicola caprae*, *Ctenocephalides caprae*, *Linognathidae caprae* and *Ripicephalus bursa* ectoparasites and ectoparasitic diseases such as bovicolosis, ctenocephalidosis, linognathosis, ripicephalosis, and *Bovicola caprae* ectoparasite as the dominant species were found to be widespread and cause

bovicolosis in goats. They are mostly found in farms where sanitary, feeding and storage conditions do not meet the requirements. during bathing and in the process of drinking water) and it was observed that they occur during all seasons of the year. It was found that high humidity and comfortable temperature in the building, lack of sunlight in the winter months, long wool of goats, poor quality feeding and dense storage create favorable conditions for the development and rapid spread of *Bovicola caprae*.

Thus, *Bovicola caprae* can be found in the body of goats in all seasons, but the extent and intensity of invasion varies according to the season, that is, the damage is at its maximum in January-February-March-April-May, and in June-July-August-September-October. minimum, it was observed to be in average condition in November-December (Table 2, Diagram 1).

The degree of infection of goats with bavicolosis by month

Table 2

T/r	The name of the dominant ectoparasitosis found	Damage by months, %											
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VII I	IX	X	XI	XII
1.	Bovikolyoz	76	82	100	100	95	11	8	6	9	12	14	28

By summarizing the damage indicators for these months, the dynamics of seasonal damage to goats with *Bovicola caprae* was determined. It was found that the average number of goats in spring is 98.3%, in winter - 62.0%, in summer - 8.0%, and in autumn - 11.6%, and it is epizootic (Table 3, Diagram 2).

Seasonal dynamics of bovicolosis in goats

Table 3

T/r	The name of the found ectoparasites	Damage by seasons, %			
		Winter	Spring	Summer	Autumn
1.	Bovicolosis	62,0	98,3	8,0	11,6

Summary.

1. Among the ectoparasites of 1,552 goats examined in Nukus District, Samarkand and Navoi Regions, Republic of Karakalpakstan, and private farms of the population, *Bovicola caprae*, *Linognathidae caprae*, *Ctenocephalides caprae*, and *Rhipicephalus bursa* species, as well as bovicolosis, ctenocephalidosis, linognathosis, and rhipicephalosis ectoparasitic diseases, from which the causative agent of bovicolosis, *Bovicola caprae*, was found to be widespread in the body of goats as the main dominant species.

2. Bovicolosis occurs in goats in all seasons. However, the incidence varies according to the season. In January-February-March-April-May, damage is maximum, June-July-August-September-October is minimum, and November-December is average. According to seasonal dynamics, 98.3% in spring, 8.0% in summer, 11.6% in autumn, 62.0% in winter, the highest damage is observed in spring and winter, and the lowest damage is observed in summer.

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